

bamate insecticides from Union Carbide, which have been effective against BPH adults in insectary studies at IRRI. FMC 35001, also a carbamate, recently has been registered for use in insect con-

trol in several countries. One of its breakdown products is carbofuran, which showed high ovicidal activity in previous IRRI experiments. NNI-750 is a novel insecticide which, according to

its manufacturer, Nihon Noyhaku, is an insect growth regulator. It is reported to have shown BPH ovicidal activity in company tests. ■

Rice ear-cutting caterpillar, an injurious pest at panicle stage

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The rice ear-cutting caterpillar *Mythimna separata* (Walk.) has become a regular rice pest, particularly at the panicle stage of the crop. The second and third generations of the pest are responsible for economic losses of grain yield in early-maturing and medium duration varieties, respectively.

The peak activity is from the last week of September to the second week of October, depending on the planting time of the crop. Observations on the pest's biology under natural conditions on caged plants of a popular variety, Kranti, were made in kharif, during September-October 1980 at Jabalpur.

In the field, the eggs generally were laid on the bottom of semidried leaves, and not near the tip, in a line under the fold of leaves where they were protected from parasitization. The egg period varied from 5 to 7 days. Immediately after hatching, the larvae first fed on dried

leaf tissues; later they fed on the green leaves. Early instars (up to 4th instar) also fed on the palea and lemma of the grain as well as on anthers of the flowers. Advanced-stage larvae (4th to 6th instars) cut and nibbled the grains and spikelets. The larval period varied from 22 to 27 days. The pupae were either naked between the tillers or in earthen cocoons in the soil near the base of the plant. The pupal period was 8-11 days. The whole life cycle from egg to adult emergence was completed in 33-45 days. ■

Sugarcane pyrilla attacking rice, and its biological control in India

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Sugarcane pyrilla or leafhopper *Pyrilla perpusilla* (Walker) (Homoptera: Fulgoroidea:Lophopidae) is a serious pest of sugarcane in northern India, and is potentially dangerous to wheat, oats, maize, bajra (pearl millet), rice, and sorghum, particularly the hybrid varieties. Sugarcane is a primary host of *P. perpusilla*.

During August-October 1978-79, a heavy incidence of sugarcane pyrilla was observed on rice in Karnal and Sonapat districts of Haryana during surveys of the pest and its natural enemies. The infested rice fields were near heavily infested sugarcane fields. Adults, nymphs, and egg masses of pyrilla were found on the rice. The pyrilla population averaged 15.5 individuals (eggs + nymphs + adults/leaf). Interestingly, the adults and nymphs of pyrilla in rice and sugarcane fields were parasitized by the larvae of the ectoparasite *Epipyrops melanoleuca* Fletcher, and the eggs were parasitized by the egg parasite *Tetrastichus pyrillae* Crawford. Parasitization

of nymphs and adults averaged 20-60% and that of eggs 75-95%. The parasites probably effectively controlled pyrilla on rice in late September 1978 and in 1979; no insecticides were applied.

A pyrilla attack was similarly heavy in rice fields adjacent to sugarcane fields in Gurdaspur district, Punjab, in August-September 1980. The pyrilla also appeared to be effectively controlled by *E. melanoleuca* and *T. pyrillar*. The two parasites keep pyrilla under control in sugarcane in Bihar, Uttar Pradesh, Haryana, Punjab, and parts of Rajasthan. The eggs and live cocoons of *E. melanoleuca* can be released in pyrilla-infested fields at 40,000-50,000 eggs/ha and 4,000-5,000 cocoons/ha when the pyrilla population averages 3.5 individuals (eggs + nymphs + adults)/leaf (the threshold level in sugarcane). ■

Egg parasitoids of rice pests in Malawi, East Africa

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During ecological investigations on rice pests in Malawi from 1971 to 1975

many parasitoids were reared from eggs collected in the fields (see table).

Trichogramma kalkae was the most important parasitoid of the stem borer *Diopsis macrophthalma*, one of the most common rice pests in Africa. It parasitized an average of 41% of the *Diopsis* eggs. *T. pinneyi* parasitized an average of 16% of *D. macrophthalma* eggs. An unidentified Sciomyzid fly was an important alternative host of *T. pinneyi*. Two other parasitoids (but of little importance) were *Trichogrammatoidea simmondsi* and a *Paracentrobia* species. (An extensive paper on the mentioned *Trichogramma* species is in press.)

Of the lepidopterous borers *Chilo djffusilineus* was parasitized mainly by *Telenomus ulliyetti* (27%) and *Trichogramma mwanzai* (7%), a recently described species.

Eggs of the pink borer *Chilo partellus* were parasitized by *T. japonicum* (33%) and *Trichogrammatoidea simmondsi* (17%). From eggs of *Thopeutis* spp. were reared *T. japonicum* (42%), *Telenomus tolli* (21%), and *T. uliyetti* (7%). Unidentified lepidopterous eggs were parasitized by another *Paracentrobia* sp. and by *Lathromeromya cercopocida*.

Experiments showed *T. kalkae* and *T. pinneyi* to be highly susceptible to pesticides such as diazinon, dimethoate, endosulfan, malathion, and phospho-

Egg parasitoids and their hosts.

Egg parasitoid	Host										
	<i>Diopsis macroph- thalma</i>	<i>Diopsis apicalis complex</i>	<i>Sepedon angularis</i>	Sciomyzid sp.	<i>Chilo diffusi- lineus</i>	<i>Chilo partellus</i>	<i>Thopeutis sp.</i>	Lepidop- teran sp.	Hemip- teran sp.	Chrysopid sp.	<i>Epicauta velata</i>
Trichogrammatidae											
<i>Trichogramma kalkae</i>	+	+ ^a	+ ^a								
<i>Trichogramma pinneyi</i>	+		+	+	+						
<i>Trichogramma mwanzai</i>					+						
<i>Trichogramma japonicum</i>						+	+				
<i>Trichogrammatoidea simmondsi</i>	+		+	+		+					
<i>Paracnrobia</i> sp.	+			+				+		+	
<i>Lathromeromya cercopida</i>								+			
Scelionidae											
<i>Telenomus ullyetti</i>					+		+		+		+
<i>Telenomus tolli</i>							+		+		+
<i>Telenomus</i> sp.									+		
Mymaridae											
<i>Anagrus</i> sp.										+	

^aOnly in the laboratory.

midon. Knockdown was 100% within 3 hours on residues of these pesticides after recommended application rates. Concentrations down to 10% of the

normal gave a total knockdown within 24 hours. The fungicide Hinosan showed no direct toxicity. In nurseries sprayed with phosphamidon the parasit-

ization of *Diopsis* eggs dropped from 60% to lower than 1%, while the number of *Diopsis* eggs hardly decreased. ■

Field control of rice caseworm with foliar insecticides

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The rice caseworm *Nymphula depunctalis* is a significant pest of flooded rice in Asia, Africa, and South America, but little published information on its control with insecticides exists. In a trial at IRRI, 11 insecticides were tested as foliar spray (0.75 kg a.i./ha) 14 days after transplanting (DT) IR40 rice to plots (2 m²) that had been hand-infested with greenhouse-reared 2d-instar larvae (4 larvae/hill) on the previous day. Each plot was surrounded with levees and plastic sheeting to prevent interplot larval movement.

Caseworm larvae are aquatic; they possess tracheal gills, and live within rice leaves folded into cases secured with silk. During the day, they float on water; at night, they climb plants to cut off leaves to make new cases or feed on severed leaves on the water surface. Cut leaves are symptomatic of caseworm feeding. As the larvae mature they skeletonize the leaf tissue of standing

Comparison of 11 foliar insecticides for control of rice caseworm based on plant damage and larval mortality. ^a IRRI, 1980.

Insecticide ^b	formulation ^c	Plant damage ^{c,d}		Larval mortality ^f (%)		
		Tillers with cut leaves (%)	Leaf scraping ^e grade 10 DS (1-9)	Plants and paddy water sprayed ^d	Only plants sprayed ^d	Only paddy water sprayed ^g
MIPC	50% WP	4.5 a	1.3 a	100 a	100 a	100 a
Triazophos	40% EC	4.6 a	1.1 a	100 a	100 a	100 a
Chlorpyrifos	40% EC	4.4 a	1.3 a	100 a	98 ab	95 ab
Azinphos-ethyl	40% EC	4.2 a	1.2 a	100 a	90 ab	100 a
BPMC	50% EC	5.1 a	1.5 a	100 a	93 ab	95 ab
Malathion	57% EC	4.2 a	1.3 a	100 a	93 ab	85 ab
Diazinon	20% EC	7.5 ab	1.2 a	100 a	98 ab	100 a
Carbaryl	85% WP	5.8 a	1.3 a	100 a	95 ab	75 bc
Phosphamidon	50% EC	5.3 a	1.3 a	95 a	83 bc	80 bc
Endosulfan	35% EC	5.1 a	1.3 a	100 a	68 c	85 ab
MTMC	50% WP	12.6 b	1.9 b	85 a	63 c	55 c
Check		23.2 c	4.2 c	5 b	0 d	0 d

^aIn a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different ($P < 0.05$). ^b0.75 kg a.i./ha 14 days after transplanting. ^cWP = wettable powder, EC = emulsifiable concentrate, DS = days after spraying. A tiller was scored as damaged if at least one leaf was cut off. ^dAv of 4 replications. ^e1-9 scale based on % leaf area scraped: 1 = none, 3 = 1-10, 5 = 11-25, 7 = 26-50, 9 = 51-100. ^f48 hours after spraying. ^gAv of 2 replications.

plants, causing the damaged leaves to turn white.

Damage to plants was scored as percentage of tillers with cut leaves and percentage of leaf tissue removed (scraped).

Within the plots, additional information was taken to compare the effect of spraying plants or paddy water separ-

ately. In the former, a hill of rice was removed from each plot immediately after spraying and moved to the greenhouse in a plot submerged in insecticide-free water. In the latter, a hill of rice was removed from each plot immediately after spraying and replaced with an insecticide-free potted hill of rice of the same age from the greenhouse. A mylar